

Effect of 2,4-D and kinetin on callus induction and plant regeneration with IR50 seeds in MS medium.

Callus induction medium				Regeneration medium ^a			
2,4-D (mg/liter)	Kinetin (mg/liter)	Seeds inoculated (no.)	Seeds producing calli (no.)	Callus production (%)	Calli transferred (no.)	Calli regenerated (no.)	Regeneration (%)
0.0	0.0	74	—	—	—	—	—
0.5	0.0	68	10	14.7	36	3	8.3
0.5	0.5	74	12	16.2	38	4	10.5
0.5	1.0	72	12	16.6	42	6	14.3
1.0	0.0	74	31	41.8	44	8	18.2
1.0	0.5	73	34	46.6	44	11	25.0
1.0	1.0	72	36	50.0	42	7	16.6
1.5	0.0	68	37	54.4	40	9	22.5
1.5	0.5	74	42	56.7	38	8	21.4
1.5	1.0	69	42	60.8	42	6	14.3
2.0	0.0	72	46	63.8	32	2	6.2
2.0	0.5	68	42	61.7	44	18	40.9 ^b
2.0	1.0	67	29	43.2	42	+	—
5.0	0.0	72	26	36.1	32	+	—
5.0	0.5	74	28	37.8	32	+	—
5.0	1.0	74	25	33.7	36	+	—

^a Regeneration medium = basal medium + 1 mg kinetin/liter + 1 mg NAA/liter. + = rhizogenesis.

^b Formation of somatic embryos.

Callus pieces were transferred to regeneration medium containing kinetin and NAA at a concentration of 1 mg/ liter each. Regeneration was better from calli induced from the C medium containing 2 mg 2,4-D/liter and 0.5 mg kinetin/ liter through the process of somatic embryogenesis (established by histological studies).

The somatic embryos formed had two distinct poles and were attached to the callus piece through their broader surface. Embryoids of different shapes were also traced out during early stages of embryogenesis. Other treatments did not yield somatic embryos. □

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A medium-duration, high-yielding, scented hybrid rice

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We have identified tall, late-maturing, scented cultivar Basmati 370 as a

complete restorer for the CMS line IR46830A.

Hybrid IR46830A/ Basmati 370 was evaluated for yield and quality components (Table 1,2). The hybrid flowered earlier and was shorter than the better parent. Positive and significant heterosis over the better parent was recorded for most characters. Increase in grain yield/ plant was due

primarily to more effective tillers/ plant and higher 1,000-grain weight. Although yield of the hybrid was not significantly higher than that of check variety Pant Dhan 4, better quality attributes make it more suitable for commercial production. Its medium growth duration would make it suitable for a rice - wheat cropping pattern. □

Table 1. Mean performance of the hybrid IR46830A/Basmati 370, and estimates of heterosis over the better parent and check variety Pant Dhan 4. ^a Pantnagar, India, 1988.

Character	Mean for F ₁	Heterosis ^b	
		Better parent	Check
Days to 50% flowering	95.0	-24.60*	-20.16*
Plant height (cm)	137.2	-12.50*	-30.66*
Effective tillers/ plant (no.)	20.8	44.45*	23.80*
Length of panicle (cm)	32.2	5.59	20.81*
Primary branches/ panicle (no.)	12.2	19.60*	-9.83
Secondary branches/ panicle (no.)	40.4	36.50*	34.50*
Spikelets/panicle (no.)	202.6	35.25*	30.20*
Grains/panicle (no.)	164.0	19.80*	17.64*
1000-grain weight (g)	22.9	31.24*	-0.62
Grain yield/plant (g)	63.0	83.89*	16.50

^a Av of 5 plants. ^b* = significant at 5% level.

Table 2. Mean value for 5 grain quality traits in Basmati 370, hybrid IR46830A/Basmati 370, and Pant Dhan 4. ^a Pantnagar, India, 1988.

Character studied	Basmati 370	Hybrid	Pant Dhan 4
Length of grain (mm)	7.88	7.38	6.34
Breadth of grain (mm)	1.72	2.04	2.10
L/B ratio	4.58	3.61	3.11
Alkali digestion value	2.25	3.00	3.50
Aroma	Strong	Intermediate	—

^a Av of 5 replications.

Evaluation of some F₁ rice hybrids developed using MR365A as CMS line

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We evaluated yield and heterosis of eight F₁ rice hybrids developed using MR365A (CMS line developed at IRRRI

Jan-May 1984. The hybrids, Cisadane, and IR36 were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 2- × 5-m plots, with 2 replications. Fertilizer was 135-45-45 kg NPK/ha.

Hybrid combinations MR365A/ IR36, MR365A/IR52, and MR365A/BR10 yielded about 1 t/ha more than Cisadane and showed significant heterosis (14.63-27.65%) (see table). For

Yield components and standard heterosis for yield in some F₁ rice hybrids evaluated in Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1984 wet season.

Hybrid	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains/panicle (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Growth duration (d)	Disease or insect score ^a		Yield ^b (t/ha)	Standard heterosis to Cisadane (%)
					GM	BLS		
MR365A/BR10	23.4	74.4	22.9	120	0	0	4.8 a	27.65
MR365A/IR36	22.8	74.2	23.0	112	1	1	4.6 a	22.87
MR365A/IR52	23.2	73.1	24.0	109	1	1	4.3 b	14.63
MR365A/IR54	23.8	64.2	23.6	116	1	1	3.5 d	-7.44
MR365A/IR60	22.0	61.4	19.8	130	1	1	3.5 d	-7.97
MR365A/IR46	21.7	79.5	23.0	132	1	5	3.4 de	-9.04
MR365A/IR26	23.5	77.7	23.5	134	1	1	3.2 e	-16.22
MR365A/IR50	22.6	62.4	21.0	120	1	1	3.2 e	-15.69
Cisadane ^c	23.7	81.9	28.9	142	1	1	3.8 c	-
IR36	22.9	83.9	20.7	120	3	3	3.6 cd	-

^a Scoring based on 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice*. GM = gall midge, BLS = bacterial leaf streak. ^b Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT

^c Best check variety.

Indonesian conditions, MR365A could be used in developing F₁ rice hybrids using IR36, JR52, and BR10 as restorer lines. However, the CMS line is not stable for pollen sterility. □

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Identification of restorers and maintainers for four CMS lines of rice

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We crossed 17 cultivars of early, medium, and late duration (as male parents) with 4 cytoplasmic genetic male sterile lines (IR46830A, IR46831A, Zhen Shan 97A, and V20A) to identify their fertility restorers and maintainers.

The F₁ seeds were germinated in petri dishes, transferred to pots, and transplanted in the field 30 d after germination.

Varieties were classified on the basis of spikelet fertility in their F₁ hybrids: restorers = >80% spikelet fertility, partial restorers = 10-79%, and

Fertility restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers for 4 CMS lines. Pantnagar, India.

CMS line	Fertility restorer	Partial restorer	Maintainer
IR46830A	Narendra 1 Saket Basmati 370	IET7613 Narendra 2 Mahsuri Govind IR58 Manhar UPR82-42 Pant Dhan 6 Manhar Pant Dhan 6 UPR79-123 Govind Saket 4 Pant Dhan 4	Ratna N22 Rasi
IR46831A	-	Manhar Pant Dhan 6 UPR79-123 Govind Saket 4 Pant Dhan 4	Pant Dhan 4
Zhen Shan 97A V20A	- -	Saket 4 Pant Dhan 4	- -

maintainers = <10%.

Narendra 1, Saket 4, and Basmati 370 were effective restorers for IR46830A. Ratna, N22, and Rasi were identified as maintainers for this CMS line (see table). Pant Dhan 4 was a maintainer

for the CMS line IR46831A.

No fertility restorer was identified for Zhen Shan 97A, V20A, and IR46831A. There was segregation for fertility in the F₁ when V20A was crossed with Pant Dhan 4. □

Media conditioning to convert nonembryogenic rice calli to embryogenic calli

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We investigated the effect of media conditioning on converting rice

nonembryogenic (NE) callus to embryogenic (E) callus.

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L. cv. S201) seeds were dehulled mechanically, surface sterilized in 5% sodium hypochloride solution for 30 min, and rinsed 3 times with sterile distilled water. Seeds were sown in basal salts and vitamins of Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium supplemented with 200 mg myo-inositol/liter, 100 mg thiamine HCl/liter, 3% (wt/vol) sucrose, and

0.7% Difco Bacto agar (pH 5.7).

Cultures were incubated under complete darkness at 22 ± 2°C.

Ten-day-old seedlings were cut in 2- to 3-mm pieces and cultured in a callus formation medium consisting of germination medium supplemented with 20 μM 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D). Five petri dishes each containing pieces of four seedlings were used per treatment. All cultures were subcultured every 4 wk.